

Experimental aquatic research infrastructures: Towards a navigation tool for supporting mesocosm-based research

Tina Heger^{1,2,3,4}, Stella A. Berger⁵, Jonathan M. Jeschke^{1,2}, Christopher Kittel⁶, Peter Kraker⁶, A. Katharina Makower⁵, Daniel Mietchen^{7,8}, Jens C. Nejstgaard⁵, Maxi Schramm⁶, Steph Tyszka^{1,2}

1 Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB), Department of Evolutionary and Integrative Ecology, Berlin, Germany

2 Freie Universität Berlin, Institute of Biology, Berlin, Germany

3 Technical University of Munich, School of Life Sciences, Freising, Germany

4 Leuphana University Lüneburg, Institute of Ecology, Lüneburg, Germany

5 Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB), Department of Plankton and Microbial Ecology, Stechlin, Germany

6 Open Knowledge Maps, Vienna, Austria

7 Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure (FIZ Karlsruhe), Berlin, Germany

8 Institute for Globally Distributed Open Research and Education (IGDORE), Jena, Germany

Abstract

Global change has strong effects on aquatic ecosystems and aquatic biodiversity. To develop more efficient mitigation measures, it is essential to perform ecological experimental research that enhances understanding of how grand ecological challenges such as pollution affect aquatic ecosystems. Aquatic experimental research infrastructures (such as aquatic mesocosms) provide efficient settings for such research, because they allow controlling environmental parameters while offering more realistic conditions than can be achieved in the laboratory. Globally, many aquatic mesocosms have been installed, and previous EU-funded projects made large steps towards more collaboration and better global accessibility of these important research infrastructures. However, it was still hard for scientists to find a mesocosm that is best suited for studying their specific research question. Further, research published in scientific journals was not systematically linked to the respective mesocosm it was performed in, and unpublished material (e.g. a description of Standard Operation Procedures) was hard to find.

With the AQUANAVI project, steps were taken to address these challenges. To achieve the project goals of enhancing discovery of information on aquatic mesocosms and related scientific publications as well as mobilizing unpublished material, we modeled and supplemented the available data, implemented pathways for open publication of this revised information, and implemented AI-based visualizations for enhancing discoverability. Specific outcomes are first versions of controlled vocabularies for describing grand ecological challenges, further research topics that are addressed with aquatic experimental studies, and controlled parameters, i.e. factors that can be manipulated in aquatic mesocosms. In addition, we developed a data model for harmonizing the description of aquatic experimental research infrastructures. This data model is centered around the mesocosm installation, which we define as the physical object, and which can be described by drawing from the developed vocabulary on controlled parameters. For allowing easy discovery of mesocosms based on this structured data, we developed the OKMaps Geo Map, which is an interactive map with integrated search and filter functionality. This discovery tool is available via a website already well-known by the research community (mesocosm.org). As a further result of the project, more than 500 publications related to mesocosm-based research are now represented in Wikidata. We developed a dedicated OAI-PMH endpoint that will - once it is fully operational - deliver publication metadata to BASE (base-search.net), making these records available for the creation of Knowledge Maps and Streamgraphs for easy discovery of mesocosm research. A further achievement of the project is the development of a template for facility descriptions as openly accessible publications in the RIO journal (riojournal.com/). This template has been developed based on feedback from the community, and will be used by facility managers to publish updated and harmonized information on their aquatic mesocosms.

Taken together, the project developed a solid basis for the implementation of an interactive atlas of aquatic mesocosm research. Next steps will be to revise the controlled vocabularies based on community feedback, to fully implement the data pipeline for allowing easy access to mesocosm-based publications with Knowledge Maps and Streamgraphs, and to apply the prepared template for producing open access publications describing specific facilities. Planned future work will further implement an interface allowing facility managers to easily update mesocosm information, developing a data pipeline for respective dynamic updates of the Geo Maps, and publishing currently unpublished documentation (e.g. SOPs) in the RIO journal. We believe the enhanced search functionality that is now available via the Geo Maps tool will already improve collaborative research and easier global access to aquatic mesocosms, thus contributing to the development of a better understanding and more efficient mitigation of grand ecological challenges in aquatic ecosystems.

1. Introduction

Aquatic ecosystems are major showcases of the biodiversity crisis. Ongoing climate change exacerbates the strong pressures that are due to other grand ecological challenges like overexploitation, pollution, and land and sea use (Macaulay et al., 2025), which are in combination leading to stark declines in aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem functioning (IPBES, 2019). Conserving and restoring aquatic ecosystems is of key importance globally, not only because they host a high diversity of species, but also because they provide vital contributions to people as e.g. provisioning of drinking water, food and energy. Current mitigation measures, including wastewater treatment and hydromorphological restoration, are not sufficient to reverse the decline of aquatic biodiversity and to revive ecosystems (Duarte et al., 2020; Dudgeon & Strayer, 2025; Haase et al., 2023). While halting and reversing the losses is still possible, this urgently requires a sound understanding of global change impacts and the development of well-suited mitigation measures.

Mechanistic understanding of ecological systems, and consequently also the development of reliable mitigation measures, is constrained by the high complexity of natural systems. A wealth of approaches has been developed for studying ecosystems, ranging from theoretical modeling to experiments in the laboratory or field, to observations of natural ecosystems. Due to the high complexity and variability of the research objects, empirical studies in ecology have to deal with a trade-off between the degrees of realism, ability to control the systems' parameters, and feasibility of replication (Gerhard et al., 2023; Macaulay et al., 2025). Laboratory experiments allow for controlled manipulation of environmental factors and replicated study designs. While laboratory settings decrease realism, this approach offers a pathway towards enhanced mechanistic understanding. Observations in natural systems, on the other hand, offer realistic settings, but the lack of control of environmental factors creates challenges for drawing conclusions about mechanistic causal relationships. Mesocosms are experimental tools that can close the gap between, on the one hand, highly controlled and replicated, but less realistic laboratory studies and, on the other hand, uncontrolled but realistic observations in natural aquatic ecosystems (Gerhard et al., 2023). Mesocosms have been defined as “experimental systems that replicate a representative natural community or ecosystem under controlled but realistic environmental conditions” (Macaulay et al., 2025). As such, they are specifically well suited for enhancing understanding of global change impacts on aquatic ecosystems and developing mitigation measures. Indeed, a recent survey amongst aquatic ecologists indicates a strong potential of mesocosm systems to address global threats to aquatic ecosystems, and a largely untapped potential for investigating solutions for mitigation of these threats (Macaulay et al., 2025).

However, to better understand and tackle global challenges, globally coordinated approaches are needed. Until the establishment of the first EU-FP7 supported network

of marine mesocosm facilities in the MESOAQUA project (#228224, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/228224/reporting>) between 2009 and 2012, mesocosm science had largely been conducted locally at individual facilities, mostly supported by local and national funds, with some collaborations across borders based on mainly personal contacts and coordination. With the establishment of the EU HORIZON2020 supported AQUACOSM (#731065) and AQUACOSM-plus (#871081) between 2017 and 2024 (www.aquacosm.eu), a first funded international network came into existence, integrating the leading mesocosm infrastructures into a coherent, interdisciplinary, and interoperable network covering all ecoregions of Europe. By connecting researchers and their facilities focusing on river, lakes, estuary or ocean ecosystems into one consortium and supporting collaborations with participants from all over the world, a great step forward was taken towards international collaboration, and standardisation of terminology, approaches and technology.

As one result of these projects, the mesocosm.org network was founded to serve as a virtual hub, providing an overview of globally available aquatic experimental research infrastructures (in the following: ‘aquatic mesocosms’, or just ‘mesocosms’) in the world. This has been an important step towards enhancing the findability of these valuable experimental research infrastructures. By clicking on the respective markers on a map at mesocosm.org, users are able to find information on the geographical location, technical specifications of each freshwater, brackish, and marine mesocosm facility, including its contact information, and scientific research topics, etc.. While the continuously gathered and updated information on worldwide aquatic mesocosm facilities was a first step, this information was not organized in a way that allowed for specific topic searching across mesocosm facilities or countries. The mesocosm.org webpage further provided a list of scientific publications stemming from research conducted at the represented aquatic mesocosm facilities. However, this information was not linked to a data structure and user interface that would allow easy search or filtering functions; nor are the listed publications linked to the respective mesocosm facility, where the study took place.

Over time, expertise needed for performing mesocosm experiments has accumulated amongst researchers and technical staff running the mesocosms. Some of this knowledge has been put together in the form of documents on ‘Standard Operation Procedures’ (SOPs). In the context of the European HORIZON2020 funded AQUACOSM and AQUACOSM-plus projects, a wiki was started for collecting such documents (wiki.mesocosm.org). However, the information given on that page currently is far from complete, hard to find and not linked to any data structure.

In conclusion, the previous EU-funded projects MESOAQUA, AQUACOSM and AQUACOSM-plus clearly paved the way towards an increase in the usage of aquatic mesocosms globally, thus contributing to enhancing the understanding of aquatic ecosystems and how they are affected by global change, and the development of

possibilities for mitigation of grand ecological challenges. However, the information that became available as a result of the projects' efforts was still incomplete, and although the projects took care to align with the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), there was still room for improvement. The information on the aquatic experimental research infrastructures was not easily *Findable*. For example, for researchers, especially if they were not part of the mesocosm community, it was hard and tedious to find out which research infrastructure is matching their needs. No globally unique and persistent identifiers were linked to the information on these infrastructures, and existing publication metadata did not contain information on linked mesocosms. The information was also not easily *Accessible*. For example, the publication lists on aquacosm.eu were designed as visually readable tables, but are not screen-reader accessible. Further, available information related to aquatic mesocosm until now was not fully *Interoperable*. Although the AQUACOSM and AQUACOSM-plus projects successfully developed a more harmonised use of scientific terms and approaches between the largely independently developed marine and freshwater realms, this process could not be fully completed during these projects. Lastly, the information was not easily *Reusable* due to a lack of clear licensing or adherence to community standards.

The project AQUANAVI (December 2024 - May 2026, part of the OSCARS project funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme) aimed at the FAIRification (i.e. improvement of the alignment with the FAIR principles) of data, publications, reports and information generated by the AQUACOSM consortium and wider community including other mesocosms worldwide, integrating them into an accessible platform and incorporating AI-driven visual discovery tools (Heger et al., 2025). The vision is to create an interactive atlas allowing scientists to explore past, present, and future contributions of aquatic experimental research and its infrastructures to address grand ecological challenges in aquatic ecosystems. Specifically, the AQUANAVI project had three goals: (i) enhancing discovery of information on aquatic mesocosms for potential users, (ii) enhancing discovery of scientific publications related to these infrastructures, and (iii) mobilizing unpublished material relevant for aquatic mesocosm research.

In the following, we will describe the developed solutions in detail, show how users can benefit from the resulting system, and point to important next steps towards a fully functional interactive atlas of aquatic mesocosm-based experimental research.

2. Project results: Overview

To achieve the project goals of enhancing discovery of information on aquatic mesocosms and related scientific publications and mobilizing unpublished material, we took the three steps of modelling and supplementing the available data, publishing

this revised information in a FAIR way, and implementing AI-based visualizations for enhancing discoverability (Fig. 1). Each of these steps will be described in further detail in the following sections, detailing also in which cases work is ongoing.

Figure 1: Summary of solutions developed in the AQUANAVI project concerning the description of aquatic experimental research infrastructures (aquatic mesocosms), scientific publications related to these mesocosm research infrastructures and unpublished material as e.g. standard operation procedures (SOPs). Dashed squares indicate work in progress.

3. Modeling and supplementing metadata on mesocosms and related publications

The starting point for FAIRifying information on aquatic mesocosms and on scientific output of mesocosm-based research was the large amount of data gathered and provided via the community-run websites mesocosm.org and aquacosm.eu. From there, information including data on the aquatic mesocosm research infrastructures and related publications was available, however, in the form of unstructured text. Further, mesocosm data was lacking consistency due to non-usage of controlled vocabularies. In the previous projects and with support from the Transnational Access Program (aquacosm.eu/transnational-access), over 600 publications have been listed including the usual metadata (e.g. author, journal, DOI, keywords); but metadata linking the published research to specific mesocosms where the respective studies had been done was not available. As a consequence, neither mesocosm nor publication metadata contained structured information on related grand ecological challenges.

As a first step towards solving these issues, we developed controlled vocabularies to make sure that the represented information will be easier to find and will become interoperable. Next, we developed a metadata schema for capturing the relevant

information in a consistent way. We then updated information on the mesocosms, and annotated a subset of the mesocosm publications accordingly.

3.1 Controlled vocabularies

To reach the goal of enhanced findability and interoperability, we developed first versions of controlled vocabularies for terms relevant in the context of mesocosm-based research. This was needed because despite a great effort was done to harmonise terminology and approaches between freshwater and marine mesocosm science environments in the EU AQUACOSM projects, the language used for describing mesocosms and the research related to them did still not have fully consistent rules and thus consisted of a mixture of a variety of natural language and technical terms, as well as longer free text snippets. The meaning of these terms and pieces of text and the relationship amongst them was often ambiguous. Creating the metadata schema (see Section 3.2) revealed three areas for which controlled vocabularies were needed: research topics (i.e. topics the mesocosm experiments relate to); grand ecological challenges (i.e. a sub-group of research topics specifying which global change factor the mesocosm research relates to) and controlled parameters (i.e. factors that can be manipulated in a mesocosm experiment). For creating the controlled vocabularies, we built on existing terminologies and amended them to match the context of mesocosm-based research.

For creating a controlled vocabulary for research topics, we analysed the terms contained in the respective fields at mesocosm.org and aquacosc.eu. Based on our experience from the AQUACOSM consortium, we inspected existing classification schemes as e.g. Balasubramanian (2019), Wikipedia’s Branches of Science (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Branches_of_science), the respective Wikidata entry (wikidata.org/wiki/Q2465832) as well as branches of science described in the context of the Hi Knowledge initiative (hi-knowledge.org/branches-of-science), and used these as a basis for developing a controlled vocabulary able to capture and classify research topics of relevance in the context of experimental research in aquatic mesocosms. Figure 2 gives an overview on the resulting controlled vocabulary; the detailed list can be found in the [Supplementary Material Table 1](#).

Figure 2: Excerpt of the controlled vocabulary for topics relevant in the context of aquatic mesocosm research. For a detailed representation, see [Supplementary Material Table 1](#). The

vocabulary developed for classifying grand ecological challenges, an additional sub-group of research topics, is shown in Figure 3.

For developing a controlled vocabulary capturing the grand ecological challenges relevant for aquatic mesocosm research, we used IPBES (2019) and Macaulay et al. (2025) as a starting point, and we additionally checked related classifications (e.g. [iucnredlist.org/resources/threat-classification-scheme](https://www.iucnredlist.org/resources/threat-classification-scheme)). We developed a hierarchical scheme containing terms relevant in the context of aquatic mesocosm research (Fig. 3). For all contained terms, we searched for existing definitions and existing identifiers in ontologies and Wikidata. Where no definition existed, we developed one ourselves. The resulting list including a glossary containing the definitions and related identifiers can be found in the [Supplementary Material Table 2](#).

Figure 3: Terms describing grand ecological challenges related to aquatic mesocosm-based research. For a full list with definitions and existing persistent identifiers, see [Supplementary Material Table 2](#).

Concerning the factors that can be manipulated in aquatic mesocosms, again the lists of terms in mesocosm.org and aquacosm.eu were the starting point. From these, we developed a hierarchical scheme of terms for capturing controlled parameters. These terms can describe factors influencing ecosystems in general, but we selected only those that can be manipulated in aquatic mesocosms. Figure 4 shows an excerpt of this scheme, and the full list can be found in the [Supplementary Material Table 3](#).

Figure 4: Excerpt of the controlled vocabulary for parameters that can be controlled in aquatic mesocosm experiments. For a detailed representation, see [Supplementary Material Table 3](#).

It has to be noted that all three controlled vocabularies contain only those terms that are relevant in the context of aquatic mesocosm-based research; they should not be understood as complete vocabularies for representing e.g. all possible research topics or all grand ecological challenges. Nonetheless, they will hopefully be useful for other research projects and initiatives, particularly those focusing on aquatic mesocosms. The current lists are suggestions developed by the authors of this publication. Future work will aim at collecting feedback from the mesocosm research community, and at developing consolidated updates of these vocabularies.

3.2 Metadata schema

For representing information relevant for describing aquatic mesocosms and related publications, we decided on a graph-based approach. In a graph database, information is represented as nodes and edges, capturing entities of interest and their relationships (Hogan et al., 2021). A main benefit of representing information in a graph data format is a strongly enhanced data connectivity, especially if controlled vocabularies are used, leading to an enhanced efficiency of searching and retrieving information.

Using the mesocosm information available at mesocosm.org and aquacosm.eu as a starting point, we developed a semantic data model for representing information on aquatic experimental research infrastructures and publications on studies conducted there in a graph-based approach. However, developing a respective data model proved more difficult than expected. For example, the aquatic experimental research infrastructures usually consist of multiple elements and are closely linked to laboratories and research institutions. In the case of CEREEP (cereep.bio.ens.psl.eu/), for example, a conglomerate of organizations are running a

facility with different mesocosm units, including ‘macrocosms’, which can also be regarded as falling under the general definition of a mesocosm as given above. Other facilities have quite different setups and use different terms to describe these setups. This made it very difficult to consolidate all these variants into one data model.

As a specific challenge, we identified the ambiguity of the term ‘facility’. In Wikidata, the term ‘facility’ can represent ‘place, equipment, or service to support a specific function’ ([wikidata.org/wiki/Q13226383](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q13226383)), and also in the colloquial use of the term, its meaning is ambiguous. For creating a data model, we regarded it as key to clearly distinguish between the physical mesocosm object (here called ‘mesocosm installation’) and the organisation that runs this physical object (here called the ‘operator’). We therefore decided against using the term ‘facility’ in the data model, while retaining it in the user interface and other presentation contexts, as it is the term most familiar to the community. In these contexts, we suggest using the term ‘facility’ for describing the combination of (a) the physical mesocosm object(s), (b) the operator, e.g. a research center or institute and (c) lab spaces etc.

Figure 5 shows a simplified representation of the metadata schema we developed. At the core of this data model is the *mesocosm installation*, which is the physical object that has a specific geolocation; it is run by an operator. Figure 5 indicates that, thanks to the graph structure, information e.g. on the operator can be drawn from any other data source and thus becomes available for characterizing the mesocosms. Mesocosm installations can be further characterized by using controlled vocabularies, such as describing the climatic conditions at the site based on the Köppen-Geiger climate classification (Kottek et al., 2006), the controlled parameters, or the research topics, including grand ecological challenges (see previous section). Every mesocosm installation has a certain size and shape, which can be specified, e.g. with information on the quantity, volume and dimension of tanks, containers or in-situ bags, or in case of running water, flumes.

Publications are a second core element in our metadata model. We regard them as separate entities described by the usual metadata (title, author(s), keywords etc.). Our metadata schema allows adding information on the mesocosm installation it relates to, the grand ecological challenges it addresses and other research topics drawn from the respective controlled vocabularies.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the developed data model.

Initially, we intended to capture as much as possible of the mesocosm installation data in Wikidata. However, during the process we realized that we needed to augment some of the data in other data sources rather than in Wikidata directly, because modeling the data fully in Wikidata was proving difficult. For example, Wikidata provides a limited number of properties, but the available ones did not fully capture what we wanted to describe. Introducing new properties, however, is not an easy process in Wikidata, requiring in-depth investigations and negotiations with the community. Also, editing items to match our needs might have interfered with the usefulness of these entries for other Wikidata users. Further, in Wikidata our data model would have been susceptible to editing from people outside of the project, who might lack an understanding of our decisions. We therefore could not be sure of keeping a data model that would be durable enough to implement.

Therefore, we created our own data store that links to existing Wikidata items whilst giving us the flexibility to model the data using different schemas and vocabularies, and amending it whenever needed. As a result, we have set up an Omeka-S instance that stores the data semantically and allows us to use various predefined vocabularies as well as creating our own. We see this as creating a good middle ground between the existing unstructured/semi-structured data and a fully open Wikidata-model version.

Our experiences revealed challenges of modelling complex data in such an open and flexible system as Wikidata.

3.3 Updating mesocosm information and annotating mesocosm publications

We used the newly developed metadata schema to transfer data from mesocosm.org and aquacosm.eu into a new data sheet. This process revealed gaps in the data, which were then filled in manually as far as possible for a subset of mesocosm facilities. We made this data available via the Geo Map (see below). For updating this information, we plan to implement a streamlined interface that would allow easy updating of the data by mesocosm managers or scientific coordinators.

The lists of publications from mesocosm.org and aquacosm.eu (see also Section 4.1) was used as a starting point for enriching publication metadata with information on related mesocosms and grand challenges. Since currently, no system is in place for automatically and reliably identifying which aquatic experimental research infrastructure the publications refer to, we had to do this manually. Within the project period we were able to add mesocosm information to the metadata of 265 (i.e. 50%) of the available publications, and information on grand ecological challenges that are addressed with the research to the metadata of 214 publications (i.e. 41%). Roughly half of these publications (105) did not refer to any grand ecological challenge. These updated metadata will be available at mesocosm.org via the Knowledge Maps (see Section 5.2), and will be fed into Wikidata and BASE to enrich the publication metadata.

4. Providing open access to the FAIRified information

In addition to improving alignment with the FAIR principles, a goal of the AQUANAVI project was to make information on aquatic mesocosms, related publications and unpublished information openly accessible. The following sections describe respective steps in this direction.

4.1 Making FAIR publication metadata openly accessible

For further FAIRifying metadata on publications reporting on research performed in the mesocosms, we retrieved publication metadata from mesocosm.org and aquacosm.eu. We merged these metadata, which resulted in a list of 526 publications. For each of these, we searched for existing entries in Wikidata, reviewed them and cleaned them as necessary, and added Wikidata entries for those publications that were missing. This metadata is extracted into a dedicated OAI-PMH endpoint, to be

harvested and processed by BASE search (base-search.net). From there, Open Knowledge Maps retrieves the data and uses it as data source for their analyses and visualisations (see Section 5). Implementing this workflow is work in progress.

4.2 Facility descriptions as open access publications

The consolidated structured and supplemented information on aquatic experimental research infrastructures (see Section 3) is made accessible via a visual search interface (Geo Maps, see below). However, a lot of information that can be valuable for potential users of aquatic mesocosms is available in the form of textual descriptions (e.g. details of the technical setup). To make this kind of information openly available as well, we developed a new publication format for aquatic mesocosm facility descriptions in the fully open journal RIO – Research Ideas and Outcomes (riojournal.com). Publishing in RIO offers several, globally unique innovations in both technological and social sides of the academic publishing practice. By using the online, collaborative [ARPHA Writing Tool](#) (formerly Pensoft Writing Tool (PWT)), we provide a pre-defined, but flexible article template to best publish the information and research outcomes of aquatic mesocosm facilities (Berger et al., submitted).

As part of the AQUANAVI project, we organised two workshops that explained how to publish information about mesocosms using the RIO format. The first workshop was organised as an online meeting in January 2026, where mesocosm experts from the AQUACOSM-RI consortium were invited. The expert group discussed possible improvements of the RIO template and format, and participants were asked for active contributions to the template as well as for showcasing their own mesocosms to test the template. During a second workshop happening in-person at the ASLO-SIL conference in Montreal, Canada, in May 2026, we introduced and promoted the updated RIO template and informed conference participants on how to use it to create publications that describe their mesocosms ([WS15 How to publish in RIO to make your Aquatic Mesocosm facility more visible](#)). This WS followed up on a talk presenting the AQUANAVI project (Berger et al., 2026) in the special session [SS082 Mesocosm-based approaches for tackling grand challenges in aquatic ecosystems](#), organised by a small team of the AQUACOSM Early-Career Researcher Network. The presentation was especially intended to showcase the AQUANAVI project and FAIRification of data and information including novel visualisation options (Geo Maps, see section 5.1) and publication formats (RIO facility descriptions). The overarching goal was thus to support the publication of materials related to aquatic mesocosms, research opportunities and experimental features in order to increase the international exchange on this important tool around the world. The template for facility descriptions will be available soon (Berger et al., submitted), and respective publications describing aquatic mesocosms are work in progress as well.

4.3 Standard Operation Procedures as open access publications

A third goal of the AQUANAVI project was to make documents that so far have been unpublished or hard to find, available for the entire research community. A prime example are Standard Operation Procedures (SOPs) that exist for any mesocosm, but are not easily findable and do not have a DOI. Publishing SOPs in the RIO journal has been discussed at the online workshop in January 2026 (see above), and experts agreed that this will be a very useful step forward to spread the knowledge contained in the SOPs to a much wider user community. Publishing these standards in the format of peer-reviewed publications would make them findable, citable and thus globally used, which would help the community to move towards methodological standardisation in mesocosm research.

SOPs have been written and finalised for the following topics:

- Data Quality Assurance and Quality Control
- Experimental Stream Mesocosm System
- High Frequency Monitoring
- How to Collaborate with the Industry
- Microbial Plankton
- Outreach Toolbox for Education on Mesocosms
- Periphyton
- Phytoplankton
- Phytoplankton Analysis with FlowCAM
- Planktonic Primary Production
- Water Chemistry
- Zooplankton

The process of publishing these SOPs in the RIO journal has been initiated.

Transforming these documents from in-house-used protocols into peer-reviewable publications made us encounter issues that need resolving first. For a correct handling of publishing figures in the SOPs that are adopted versions from various sources, the copyright licences need to be clarified. Furthermore, the use of ambiguous or unclear references cited in the SOPs has to be considered for further publications of the SOPs in peer reviewed journals. These and more issues will be included in a document summarizing guidance information that will be made available for all authors of the existing yet unpublished mesocosm SOPs.

5. Enhancing discoverability of mesocosms and publications

An important further aim of the AQUANAVI project was to improve the discoverability of aquatic mesocosms and their associated research output. To achieve this aim, we developed a geographical discovery tool for mesocosms and integrated visual discovery services for research outputs. Together, these services enable users to identify suitable aquatic experimental research infrastructures, explore their characteristics and the expertise located there, and discover related scientific outputs through intuitive visual interfaces.

5.1 Geo Maps

As discussed in the Introduction, information about aquatic mesocosms from the MESOAQUA, AQUACOSM and AQUACOSM-plus projects is distributed across two websites and not accessible within one interface. Furthermore, existing discovery interfaces lack advanced search functionality. To address these challenges, Open Knowledge Maps developed a Geo Map (Open Knowledge Maps, 2026a) that provides a central access point for exploring mesocosms and their characteristics based on the international mesocosm network (see mesocosm.org/facilities).

The development of the Geo Map was guided by a user-centred design process, including an evaluation of mesocosm metadata, the identification of user needs, and the definition of a primary usage scenario. Two main user groups were identified:

1. Researchers seeking suitable aquatic mesocosms for conducting specific experiments, or searching for related publications and data.
2. Infrastructure operators aiming to increase the visibility of their aquatic experimental research infrastructures and to attract researchers and stakeholders.

The primary usage scenario was the identification of active aquatic mesocosms suitable for a particular research project. To support this scenario, the system needed to provide information on the purpose and capabilities of respective mesocosms, available expertise, instrumentation and measurement capabilities, as well as thematic areas of research. These requirements, together with the overarching goal of making mesocosm information better accessible to the broader scientific community and other stakeholders, informed both the metadata model and the design of the user interface. To facilitate interoperability with the broader AQUANAVI discovery infrastructure, Open Knowledge Maps developed metadata recommendations and mappings between mesocosm metadata and the schema used by the discovery services.

The Geo Map follows Shneiderman’s visual information-seeking mantra of “overview first, zoom and filter, then details-on-demand” (Shneiderman, 1996). Mesocosms are represented as pins on an interactive map and as entries in a synchronised list view (Figure 6). Users can navigate the map, zoom into regions of interest, and switch between standard, humanitarian and topographical map layers. A search function enables filtering across mesocosm metadata, allowing users to quickly identify mesocosms matching specific research topics, equipment, controlled parameters, expertise, or grand ecological challenges. Both the map and list views are updated dynamically based on the selected search criteria.

Selecting a mesocosm reveals key metadata, including a description of the mesocosm, available equipment, controlled parameters, research topics, related grand ecological challenges, keywords and a link to the corresponding mesocosm.org entry. There, users can access additional information such as mesocosm images, lodging options and further details about the infrastructure. The Geo Map also provides sharing, citation and embedding functionalities, allowing the visualisation to be referenced and reused in external websites and publications.

Figure 6: Geo Map of aquatic mesocosms (Open Knowledge Maps, 2026a).

The Geo Map was implemented as a new visualisation type within the open-source Head Start framework developed by Open Knowledge Maps. Following an evaluation of open-source geospatial visualisation libraries against user, usability and technical requirements, the Leaflet JavaScript library was selected as the foundation for the implementation. Integrating Leaflet required extensions to the Head Start architecture, including new frontend components for map rendering, navigation and interaction, as well as synchronisation between the map and metadata list views. In addition,

dedicated data transformation and enrichment workflows were developed to enable the integration of mesocosm information into the visualisation framework.

The Geo Map supports multiple map layers, interactive filtering and search functionalities, and configurable display options. Geospatial information is rendered using publicly available map data from OpenStreetMap and OpenTopoMap. The resulting service provides a dedicated discovery environment that improves the visibility and accessibility of aquatic mesocosm infrastructures for researchers and other stakeholders.

5.2 Knowledge maps and streamgraphs

In addition to infrastructure discovery, AQUANAVI aims to improve the findability of research outputs associated with aquatic mesocosm-based research at the facilities. To support this objective, existing visual discovery services from Open Knowledge Maps will be integrated in the mesocosm.org website. An embedded search interface connected to the BASE API (see Section 4.1) will enable users to generate Knowledge Maps and Streamgraphs based on the research outputs available through the project.

Knowledge Maps provide a visual overview of a research topic based on the most relevant publications matching a user query (see Figure 7). Using text similarity analysis, publications are automatically grouped into thematic areas represented as clusters on the map. Area labels are generated from characteristic keywords and phrases that frequently occur within a cluster while being less common in others (Kraker et al., 2019). This approach enables users to quickly identify major research themes, explore relationships between topics and access relevant publications directly from the visualisation.

Figure 7: Knowledge Maps of aquatic experimental research infrastructures (Open Knowledge Maps, 2026b)

Complementing the Knowledge Maps, Streamgraphs (Byron & Wattenberg, 2008) provide a temporal perspective on the research landscape. Based on publications matching a query, the visualisation identifies the most prominent keywords and displays their occurrence over time as flowing streams. The relative height of each stream reflects the prominence of a topic within the retrieved corpus during a given period. Streamgraphs support the exploration of thematic developments and emerging trends, enabling users to analyse how research interests have evolved over time.

Both visualisation types were previously developed within Open Knowledge Maps and were adapted for use within AQUANAVI through integration with the project's repository infrastructure and discovery workflows. Together, they will complement the Geo Map by providing visual access to the scientific outputs associated with aquatic mesocosm-based research. This integrated approach forms a central component of the AQUANAVI vision: by combining geographical, topical and temporal perspectives, the AQUANAVI discovery services support the exploration of both research infrastructures and the knowledge they generate (Kraker et al., 2026).

5.3 Delivering the new search functionalities to the community

We integrated the Geo Maps service at the mesocosm.org website, which is already well known within the mesocosm research community. Currently, the Geo Maps draw from a static dataset containing updated and enriched metadata of a sub-set of mesocosm facilities. To introduce and test the newly developed discovery tools, we launched a questionnaire at the online workshop in January 2026, where experts from the AQUACOSM-RI community were invited. After the introduction talk about the AQUANAVI project, the Geo Map and its new functionality were presented and a feedback session with all participants was organised, giving the following results:

- Mesocosms, related publications, methods and SOP, keyword search, datasets, geographical search and visualisation all were regarded as important focal topics.
- As objectives for using the Geo Map, the experts mentioned contacts for collaborations, literature review, meta-analyses, reproducibility studies and possibilities for coordinated experiments and collaboration.
- Workshop participants preferred to see direct links to publications and datasets and downloadable packages of selected subsets of publications.
- Concerning search options, workshop participants pointed out as relevant: mesocosm characteristics (flume, benthic, freshwater, etc.), geographical information (incl. climate zone, continent, country, geolocation, etc.), groups of organisms, research focus, methods, publication keywords, publication years, information on SOPs, equipments and quality control protocols available for download.

- Familiarity with Wikidata was mixed among participants.

Further, it was discussed how to report on the duration of functional mesocosms (e.g. when it opened and whether it is still active), or how to alert the community that a new aquatic experimental research infrastructure was added.

To make sure that the newly developed discovery tools become well-known in the community of researchers using aquatic mesocosms, we advertised them during the above-mentioned ASLO-SIL conference in Montreal, Canada, in May 2026. Importantly, we also integrated them in the mesocosm.org website, which is already well known within the mesocosm research community.

The usefulness of the [Geo Map navigation tool](#) can be illustrated by an example: imagine a researcher who is preparing a proposal around heat wave impacts on plankton communities and wants to conduct heatwave exposures of natural planktonic communities using mesocosm facilities across a latitudinal gradient. The new Geo Map navigation tool enables the person to find the information on respective mesocosm facilities with heat wave applications and the possible access availability and contacts (see Fig. 8).

The screenshot shows the mesocosm.org website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: Home, About, Bibliography, Facilities, AQUACOSM, Contact, and Working with Mesocosms. Below the navigation bar, the main heading is "Geo Map of aquatic mesocosm facilities" with a sub-heading "98 resources" and "Data source: AQUANAVI Until 21 Jan 2026". There are filters for "Resource types", "All lang", and "Data quality". A search bar on the right contains the text "heat wave". The map on the left shows a world map with several black location pins. On the right, the search results are displayed, showing three entries for "Archipelago Benthic Mesocosm Network" and one for "BMMF - Bermuda Marine Mesocosm Facility". Each entry includes a link to the facility page and a brief description. For example, the Archipelago Benthic Mesocosm Network is described as "Outdoor infrastructure consisting of 40 independent 600-liter tanks distributed across two marine field stations in the Archipelago Sea (Skärgårdscentrum Korpoström, 20 tanks) and the Åland...". Each entry also has an "Export" button.

Figure 8: The search term “heat wave” revealed 11 matching mesocosm facilities, displaying their geolocation on the Geo Map.

6. Conclusions and outlook

In times of ongoing steep declines of aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem functionality, it is an urgent need to make full use of available experimental research infrastructures that help address knowledge gaps concerning understanding and mitigation of grand ecological challenges' effects on aquatic ecosystems. With the AQUANAVI project, we took important steps towards enhanced discoverability of aquatic experimental research infrastructures, related scientific publications, and unpublished material important for conducting mesocosm experiments. On the community-wide known website mesocosm.org, researchers can now visually discover existing aquatic mesocosm research infrastructures and retrieve useful related information accessible within one interface (mesocosm.org/facilities/). A keyword search allows identifying those aquatic mesocosms that match the experimental needs of users. Since we added information on which grand ecological challenges can be addressed in an aquatic mesocosm to the metadata, users can now specifically search for aquatic experimental research infrastructures that have the capacity to host experiments of the desired topic. This will enhance developing and understanding mitigation strategies for aquatic ecosystems under the pressure of global change.

While much has been achieved in the AQUANAVI project, given the limited budget and time, some tasks require further work, as pointed out above already (Fig. 1). Further, we identified several topics that would be important to pursue in future projects to reach a maximally cost-effective outcome from the investments already done in the related projects MESOAQUA, AQUACOSM, AQUACOSM-plus and AQUANAVI. First, the data source for the Geo Map tool is currently a static database that so far needs to be updated manually. Ideally, facility managers could submit updates or new entries via an easily accessible form, which would then lead to automatic updates of the Geo Map. This functionality would require implementing the aforementioned form, developing a data pipeline for respective dynamic updates of the Geo Map, and corresponding adaptations on the Open Knowledge Maps side to ingest the updated metadata, refresh the Geo Map data, and ensure that changes are reflected reliably in the public interface. Further, it would be useful to add a climate map as a layer in addition to the available standard, humanitarian and topographical map layers.

Second, a goal for future work should be to extend the corpus of mesocosm publications, ideally by introducing a semi-automated workflow for retrieving and enriching the required publication metadata, and making them available for creating Knowledge Maps and Streamgraphs. So far, the controlled vocabularies have not been fully leveraged for annotating the publication metadata, and developing workflows for doing this is a further task for a future project.

An interesting path to pursue would further be to establish a system and workflow for assigning persistent identifiers to the mesocosm installations. Recent work has

introduced a metadata schema and persistent identifiers for instruments (Krahl et al., 2021; Stocker et al., 2020), and future work should explore how to leverage this work for the context of mesocosm installations.

In conclusion, the AQUANAVI project took important steps towards further FAIRification of information around aquatic experimental research infrastructures. While the Geo Maps already provide functionalities that are very useful for the community, the developed data model and controlled vocabularies lay the ground for a powerful FAIR digital infrastructure. Once this infrastructure is fully implemented, it will allow to fully leverage the work that has been done in the previous EU-funded projects MESOAQUA, AQUACOSM and AQUACOSM-plus. We are convinced that the resulting interface will motivate further global mesocosm-based research, especially in cooperative settings, aimed at understanding and mitigating grand ecological challenges. It will thus become possible to fully leverage the potential of all existing aquatic experimental research infrastructures, thus allowing to overcome the biodiversity crisis in aquatic ecosystems.

7. Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the OSCARS project, which has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751.

This work was supported by the EU H2020-INFRAIA project (No. 871081) AQUACOSM-plus: Network of Leading Ecosystem Scale Experimental AQUATIC MesoCOSM Facilities Connecting Rivers, Lakes, Estuaries and Oceans in Europe and beyond - funded by the European Commission, and the EU H2020-INFRAIA project (No. 731065) AQUACOSM: Network of Leading European AQUATIC MesoCOSM Facilities Connecting Mountains to Oceans from the Arctic to the Mediterranean - funded by the European Commission.

8. References

- Balasubramanian, M. (2019). Economic value of regulating ecosystem services: A comprehensive at the global level review. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 191(10), 616. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-019-7758-8>
- Berger, S.A, Nejstgaard, J.C., A. Makower, K., Feuchtmayr, H., Mietchen D., Jeschke J., Heger T., (submitted). Template for an *Aquatic Mesocosm Facility Description* paper. *Submitted to Research and Innovation and Outcome*.
- Berger, S. A., Nejstgaard, J.C., Makower, K., Heger, T., Jeschke, J., Kittel, C., Kraker, P., Mietchen, D., Schramm, M., & Tyszka, S. (2026). *AQUANAVI: A New Navigation Tool for Aquatic Mesocosm-Based Research To Address Grand Challenges and Their Mitigation*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.20830359>

- Byron, L., & Wattenberg, M. (2008). Stacked Graphs – Geometry & Aesthetics. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 14(6), 1245–1252. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2008.166>
- Duarte, C. M., Agusti, S., Barbier, E., Britten, G. L., Castilla, J. C., Gattuso, J.-P., Fulweiler, R. W., Hughes, T. P., Knowlton, N., Lovelock, C. E., Lotze, H. K., Predragovic, M., Poloczanska, E., Roberts, C., & Worm, B. (2020). Rebuilding marine life. *Nature*, 580(7801), 39–51. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2146-7>
- Dudgeon, D., & Strayer, D. L. (2025). Bending the curve of global freshwater biodiversity loss: What are the prospects? *Biological Reviews*, 100(1), 205–226. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.13137>
- Gerhard, M., Koussoroplis, A.-M., Raatz, M., Pansch, C., Fey, S. B., Vajedsamiei, J., Calderó-Pascual, M., Cunillera-Montcusí, D., Juvigny-Khenafou, N. P. D., Polazzo, F., Thomas, P. K., Symons, C. C., Beklioglu, M., Berger, S. A., Chefaoui, R. M., Ger, K. A., Langenheder, S., Nejstgaard, J. C., Ptacnik, R., & Striebel, M. (2023). Environmental variability in aquatic ecosystems: Avenues for future multifactorial experiments. *Limnology and Oceanography Letters*, 8(2), 247–266. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/lo2.10286>
- Haase, P., Bowler, D. E., Baker, N. J., Bonada, N., Domisch, S., Garcia Marquez, J. R., Heino, J., Hering, D., Jähnig, S. C., Schmidt-Kloiber, A., Stubbington, R., Altermatt, F., Álvarez-Cabria, M., Amatulli, G., Angeler, D. G., Archambaud-Suard, G., Jorrín, I. A., Aspin, T., Azpiroz, I., ... Welti, E. A. R. (2023). The recovery of European freshwater biodiversity has come to a halt. *Nature*, 620(7974), 582–588. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06400-1>
- Heger, T., Berger, S., Jeschke, J., Kittel, C., Kraker, P., Makower, A., Mietchen, D., Nejstgaard, J., & Schramm, M. (2025). AQUANAVI: Navigating Grand Challenges and their Mitigation using Aquatic Experimental RIs. *Research Ideas and Outcomes*, 11, e176476. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.11.e176476>
- Hogan, A., Blomqvist, E., Cochez, M., d'Amato, C., de Melo, G., Gutierrez, C., Labra Gayo, J. E., Kirrane, S., Neumaier, S., Polleres, A., Navigli, R., Ngonga Ngomo, A.-C., Rashid, S. M., Rula, A., Schmelzeisen, L., Sequeda, J., Staab, S., & Zimmermann, A. (2021). Knowledge Graphs. In *ACM Comput. Surv.* (Bd. 54, Nummer 4, S. Article 71). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3447772>
- IPBES. (2019). *Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (E. Brondizio, S. Diaz, J. Settele, & H. T. Ngo, Hrsg.; Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6417333>
- Kottek, M., Grieser, J., Beck, C., Rudolf, B., & Rubel, F. (2006). World Map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification updated. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, 15(3), 259–263. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2006/0130>
- Krahl, R., Darroch, L., Huber, R., Devaraju, A., Klump, J., Habermann, T., Stocker, M., & The Research Data Alliance Persistent Identification of Instruments Working

- Group members. (2021). *Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments*. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00070>
- Kraker, P., Berger, S. A., Nejtgaard, J. C., Makower, K., Heger, T., Jeschke, J. M., Kittel, C., Mietchen, D., Schramm, M., & Tyszka, S. (2026, März 14). *AQUANAUI: A New Navigation Tool for Aquatic Mesocosm-Based Research To Address Grand Challenges and Their Mitigation*. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu26-14079>
- Kraker, P., Schramm, M., & Kittel, C. (2019). Open Knowledge Maps: Visuelle Literatursuche basierend auf den Prinzipien von Open Science. *Mitteilungen der Vereinigung Österreichischer Bibliothekarinnen und Bibliothekare*, 72(2), 460–477. <https://doi.org/10.31263/voebm.v72i2.3202>
- Macaulay, S. J., Jeppesen, E., Riebesell, U., Nejtgaard, J. C., Berger, S. A., Lewandowska, A. M., Rico, A., Kefford, B. J., Vad, C. F., Costello, D. M., Wang, H., Madge Pimentel, I., Barcelos e Ramos, J., González, J., Spilling, K., de Senerpont Domis, L., Boersma, M., Stockenreiter, M., Meerhoff, M., ... Piggott, J. J. (2025). Addressing grand ecological challenges in aquatic ecosystems: How can mesocosms be used to advance solutions? *Oikos*, 2025(5), e11020. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.11020>
- Open Knowledge Maps. (2026a). *Geo Map of aquatic mesocosm facilities* [Datensatz]. <https://openknowledgemaps.org/geomap/251058f5e8c0c751ad10d42981c0430e&embed=true>
- Open Knowledge Maps. (2026b). *Knowledge Map of research on aquatic experimental research facilities* [Datensatz]. <https://openknowledgemaps.org/map/6762824c9702fccf31e01f63fa8a0432>
- Shneiderman, B. (1996). The eyes have it: A task by data type taxonomy for information visualizations. *Proceedings 1996 IEEE Symposium on Visual Languages*, 336–343. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VL.1996.545307>
- Stocker, M., Darroch, L., Krahl, R., Habermann, T., Devaraju, A., Schwardmann, U., D’Onofrio, C., & Häggström, I. (2020). Persistent Identification of Instruments. *Data Science Journal*, 19, 18. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-018>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>